

NONDESTRUCTIVE EVALUATION OF PULL-OUT STRENGTH OF REINFORCING FIBRES

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ABSTRACT

The correlation is examined between a series of pull-out tests on a steel wire embedded in a cylinder of EPON-815 resin and ultrasonic scattering measurements. The ultrasonic results are evaluated using a wave propagation model, that shows a drop in the effective interfacial spring constants linking the wire to the resin matrix as successively larger pull-out loads are applied. These results indicate the potential for using ultrasonics to monitor the condition of the fibre/matrix interface in a fibre-reinforced composite material.

INTRODUCTION

The strength and stiffness of a fibre-reinforced composite material is highly dependent on the strength of the interfacial bond that links each fibre to the matrix material. The quality of this interfacial bond can be compromised in several ways during the manufacturing process, such as improper control of temperature or pressure during the curing cycle, residual stress effects, or contamination on the surface of the fibres. Further deterioration of the interface may occur during the service life of the material. Under these circumstances, it would be highly advantageous to have a nondestructive method of characterizing the fibre-matrix interface. In particular, it is important that this characterization be in the form of a quantitative estimate of the force required to pull out the fibres. The objective of this study is to investigate the capability of an ultrasonic technique for providing this quantitative estimate.

To date, the destructive evaluation of pull-out strength and ultrasonic characterization of fibres embedded in a matrix have been pursued largely as two separate disciplines. Piggott [1] has explored the use of pull-out strength measurements on fibre-polymer systems to study the effects of composite processing parameters on the quality of the interface; however, the technique is destructive and is limited to the study of relatively short lengths of embedded fibre to avoid fibre breakage during pull-out.

The use of ultrasound to characterize cylinders has been studied for over 50 years, in large part motivated by the naval defense priority of classifying sonar echoes of submarines. Sinclair *et al* [2] examined the use of a normal mode expansion technique for characterizing echoes from SCS6 fibres

Figure 1. Broadband compression wave, normally incident on cylindrical specimen.

embedded in a titanium alloy matrix. Although the large experimental variations in the fibre's ultrasonic diffraction pattern were suspected to originate from an unevenness in the fibre-matrix interface, no direct correlation was made with the fibre pull-out strength. A numerical model of wave propagation in the composite has been recently extended to explicitly account for reduced radial or tangential stiffness in the interface [3]; there is now the potential for estimating interfacial degradation based on ultrasonic wave diffraction studies. In this paper, these principles will be applied to the study of a 1.6 mm diameter steel wire embedded in an EPON-815 plastic matrix.

THEORY

Consider an infinite plane compressional wave normally incident on an immersed cylindrical section of matrix material of outer radius a containing a single reinforcing fibre of radius b , as shown in Figure 1. The wave forms multiple circuits about the system, and excites resonant modes of vibration; each resonance is characterized by the number of wavelengths spanning the closed loop over which the resonant wave pattern is generated. A numerical model of this phenomenon is based on a solution of the wave equation in each of the three media (reinforcing fibre, matrix material, and water path) as an infinite expansion of normal modes, using interfacial boundary conditions to solve for the unknown expansion coefficients.

Following [4], the scattered wave pressure p_s in the fluid is expressed in terms of Hankel functions of the first kind of order n :

$$p_s = \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} C_n \epsilon_n i^n H_n^{(1)}(kr) \cos(n\theta) \quad (1)$$

where ϵ_n is the Neumann factor, $i = \sqrt{-1}$, k is the compression wave number, and r the distance from the central axis. A solution for all the unknown coefficients C_n must be determined by using potential theory to solve the differential wave equation, as a function of compression wavenumber k , in each of the three media. Attenuation effects in the epoxy were included via imaginary components β_L and β_S .

of the compression and shear wave numbers, respectively, where $\beta_{L,S}$ represents the ratio of imaginary to real wavenumber components. [5] The following boundary conditions are applied to link the three media.

1. At the water-matrix interface: continuity of normal stress and normal displacement, shear stress equals zero.
2. At the matrix-fibre interface: normal and shear interfacial stresses are each equivalent to the step discontinuity in normal and shear displacement, respectively, multiplied by a corresponding interfacial spring constant. The values of these effective interfacial spring constants, K_r for normal stress and K_θ for shear stress, characterize the stiffness (and are possibly related to the strength) of the interfacial bond.

The solution to this system of equations is given elsewhere [6], it allows the diffracted wave pressure to be predicted at any (r,θ) location relative to the axis of the reinforcing fibre. This pressure, normalized by the amplitude of the incident wave, can then be plotted against the non-dimensional frequency ka , where a is the outer radius of the specimen. Resonant frequencies are clearly identified by sharp dips in the diffraction spectrum. An excellent match can be obtained between experimentally measured diffraction spectra and those calculated from Eqn (1), provided realistic values of material constants and interfacial spring constants are used in the numerical model. In fact, final estimates for these material parameters are normally obtained by matching the numerically calculated resonant frequencies to those measure experimentally. It is expected that only the values of the spring constants K_r and K_θ would vary significantly as functions of processing conditions or service damage to an engineering component.

EXPERIMENTAL SAMPLES

For this study, it was desired to use experimental specimens that met the following criteria:

- (i) The matrix material should be transparent, so that a visual inspection may be made of the condition of the fibre/matrix interface. Also, it would facilitate the detection of any fibre breakage.
- (ii) The specimens must be amenable to ultrasonic characterization. This implies that there must be a minimum length of several millimetres of embedded fibre within the matrix to be irradiated with ultrasound as shown in Figure 1.
- (iii) The fibre must have a sufficiently high strength such that a pull-out test can be conducted without breaking the fibre.

The above conditions are met by a 1.592 mm diameter cold-worked tool-steel wire embedded in EPON-815 plastic resin. Although the large diameter of the wire is not characteristic of most high performance fibre-reinforced composite materials, the results of the ultrasonic tests can easily be scaled down to accommodate fibres of much smaller diameter.

A disposable cylindrical mould was fabricated with a single wire running along the axis. The epoxy was poured into the mould and allowed to completely harden. The mould was then removed and the epoxy machined down to a diameter of 8.131 mm. The machining process was controlled to ensure that any eccentricity of the wire was less than 3%. The sample was then cut to yield a final embedded fibre length of 25 mm, with the fibre protruding by 8 mm from one end of the specimen, the protruding fibre was required to accommodate the pull-out tests.

Figure 2. Experimental set-up for measuring diffraction spectrum of test specimen.

In order to ultrasonically monitor any degradation of the specimen's interface, it was necessary to first completely characterize the material properties of the fresh specimen. A schematic of the equipment setup is shown in Figure 2. The specimen was irradiated with broadband ultrasonic pulses with a central frequency of 1.0 MHz, using an immersion transducer in a pulse-echo configuration. The diffracted signal was then picked up by the same transducer, and after being amplified by the pulser/receiver module it was digitized and sent to a personal computer for processing. The signal was Fast Fourier transformed and deconvolved with a reference waveform to produce a normalized diffraction pattern as a function of frequency. The result is shown in Figure 3a. As expected, the diffraction spectrum shows several resonance dips whose frequencies are determined by the radii and stiffness properties of the reinforcing fibre and EPON-815 layer.

The numerical model was then applied to this same specimen, in an attempt to duplicate the set of resonance frequencies that had been measured experimentally. The radii of the steel fibre and plastic resin were used in the calculations. Values of the interfacial constants K_r and K_θ were found to be very high, indicative of a high quality interface at which there would be close continuity of stress and displacement across the boundary line. Iterations were then performed on the values of the elastic constants of the EPON-815, to locate values for which the numerical prediction of resonance frequencies would match the experimental measurements. Table 1 shows the material constants thereby determined for the EPON-815, plus elastic constants for the steel core.

PULL-OUT AND ULTRASONIC TESTS

The embedded steel wire sample was subjected to succession of pull-out tests of increasing load, each test followed by a measurement of the ultrasonic diffraction spectrum. Four such sets of tests were conducted, corresponding to applied loads of 0, 30, 50, and 70 kg to the wire; the wire broke loose from its matrix at the final applied load of 70 kg, as revealed by a sudden drop-off of the load

simultaneous with a large measured axial displacement of the steel wire. Visual examination of the interfacial region through the EPON-815 as the pull-out trials proceeded produced no information that could be correlated with measurements of applied load or ultrasonic tests.

Figure 3a shows the diffraction spectrum from the sample in the as-fabricated condition. Figure 3b shows the measured spectrum from the same sample after application of the 30 kg load. Also shown in Figure 3b is the numerical calculation of the spectrum, determined by adjusting the values of the two interfacial spring constants to yield a close match with the experimental resonance frequencies. Little change in the spectrum was observed after the next loading increment up to 50 kg. Figure 3c shows the experimentally measured and calculated spectra after the load was increased to the failure level of 70 kg.

Values of the interfacial constants K_r and K_θ calculated after each loading stage are shown in Table 2. Due to the limited sensitivity of most resonances to the values of the spring constants, it was not possible in this limited set of trials to determine values of the two spring constants independently of each other. Instead, it was assumed that the pull-out trials caused similar perturbations in the interfacial transmission efficiency of both shear and compressional waves, via the two spring constants. This issue will require further exploration in the future, as it should not be expected in general that the same values would exist for K_r and K_θ .

Table 1. Interfacial Spring Constants in EPON-815/Steel System

	EPON-815 resin	steel wire
outer diameter (mm)	8.131	1.592
density (kg/m ³)	1177	9449
Lamé constant λ (GPa)	5.06	140
Lamé constant μ (GPa)	1.7	94
β_p, β_s (Nepers)	0.009, 0.015	-

Table 2. Interfacial spring constants, after application of successive pull-out loads

Maximum applied pull-out load before ultrasonic spectrum measurement	Calculated value of K_r, K_θ (N/m ³)
0	1×10^{15}
30 kg	9×10^{13}
50 kg	9×10^{13}
70 kg	2×10^{13}

Figure 3. Experimental and calculated diffraction spectrum magnitude, plotted against normalized frequency ka , after pull-out trials of:

Figure 3a: 0 kg, for which interfacial spring constants $K_r = K_0 = 10^{15} N/m^3$;

Figure 3b: 30 kg, for which interfacial spring constants $K_r = K_0 = 9 \times 10^{13} N/m^3$;

Figure 3c: breaking load of 70 kg, for which interfacial spring constants $K_r = K_0 = 2 \times 10^{13} N/m^3$

The resonance that is most significantly perturbed by the successive pull-out trials originates from an interfacial wave, at approximately $ka=24$ (noted by arrow in Figure).

Experimental measurement — ; Calculated from Eqn (1) - - - -

ANALYSIS

The ultrasonic tests indicate that there was initial damage done to the fibre-matrix interface with the first applied pull-out load of 30 kg, and then little additional damage until the final failure load of 70 kg was applied. It is noted that because the wavelength of the ultrasonic beam was of the order of 1-2 mm, it is not theoretically possible to resolve damage zones that are substantially smaller than 2 mm. In reality, the relatively wide profile of the ultrasonic beam resulted in a spatially-averaged result being achieved, i.e., an effective average value of the interfacial spring constants integrated over at least 1 cm of fibre length. This limitation rendered it impossible to study the progression of interfacial damage along the length of the embedded fibre, noted in other studies. [7] It is noted that this spatial resolution problem might be less severe when examining fibres of the order of 100 microns or less in diameter, as the ultrasonic tests would be conducted with high frequency sound, using beam profiles with a diameter of the order of 1 mm.

It was found that increasing the values of spring constants beyond 10^{15} had minimal effect - it appears that these values of spring constants ensured close to total continuity of normal and shear displacement across the interface. It is interesting to note, however, the general shift of all resonances to slightly higher frequencies after the pull-out tests at 30 and 70 kg; the pull-out tests are believed to have caused a minor perturbation in the thickness of the EPON-815 layer, which manifested itself as a shift in the resonance pattern. It is also noted that the resonance that was most sensitive to the pull-out trials occurred at a value of normalized frequency ka equal to about 24; numerical analysis indicates that this resonance originates from an interfacial wave travelling primarily along the plastic/steel boundary.

Although this series of tests has indicated the potential for correlating ultrasonic tests with damage caused by pull-out trials, there is still an incomplete understanding as to the exact nature of the damage achieved with sub-critical loads (30 kg and 50 kg in this case). It is recommended that these tests be combined with destructive examination of the interface in order to bridge this gap.

CONCLUSION

A series of pull-out trials on a steel wire embedded in EPON-815 resin has been correlated with a parallel set of ultrasonic tests. The results showed a drop in the effective interfacial spring constants after successively increasing pull-out loads were applied, although the correlation between load level and change in spring constant value was far from linear. Numerical simulations of the ultrasonic diffraction characteristics of the sample showed good correlation with experiment, and were able to trace the interfacial damage to the sample as the pull-out load increased. After further trials of this type, coupled with destructive examination of damage to the interface as a function of applied load, it is recommended that the ultrasonic technique be applied to samples with smaller, more realistic fibre diameters, embedded in metal or ceramic matrices. It remains to explore the relative contribution of the interfacial spring constants K_r and K_θ in describing the damage caused by the pull-out trials.

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